
Young Geotechnical Engineers Research Forum, 1999

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The forum was held during a meeting of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland at Clyde Road on 1st November 1999.

SYNOPSIS

The paper includes an initial overview of geotechnical research in Ireland and is followed by eight summaries of research programmes currently underway at Irish Universities.

1.0 Introduction (Dr. Barry Lehane, TCD)

Research in civil engineering at Irish Universities has grown significantly in recent years primarily because of the increase in the numbers of students wishing to obtain a post-graduate qualification. Research output has been placed high on the list of priorities of the Higher Education Authority and the academics have responded partly because their career development is linked strongly to research output.

Post-graduate research in geotechnics has benefited from the desire of students to perform post-graduate studies and, as shown on Figure 1, there are now typically about twelve MSc/PhD degrees awarded every year to students who have specialised in a geotechnical area. This number is several times that of 10 or 20 years ago and is comparable to the annual number of post-graduate research degrees currently being awarded in structural engineering..

The significant research achievements of young geotechnical researchers at our universities prompted the Geotechnical Society of Ireland (GSI) to run the first Young Geotechnical Researchers forum in 1999. In all, eleven presentations were made and this paper contains a two page summary of eight of these presentations. The presentations given by Claire Glynn (UCD), Carl Branagh (UCD) and Chisco Ruis (UCD) are not summarised. Each of the summaries was written by the research students. These were subsequently edited to suit the format presented here.

The GSI also run an annual forum with participants from both Industry and the universities. This forum is used to select an Irish representative for the European Young Geotechnical Engineers Conference.

2.0 Declan Phillips (PhD student at TCD, Lecturer WIT)

Introduction

This article highlights some findings from a research programme presently underway at a Dept. of the Environment (N. Ireland) site at Kinnegar, which is about 10km north of Belfast. This site has almost inadvertently become the first geotechnical test bed site in Northern Ireland. A programme of research has evolved at the site over the last four years and has included lateral load tests and combined lateral & vertical load tests on instrumented driven precast concrete single piles

The Institution of Civil Engineers in London awarded the Project team an ICE 'Research & Development Enabling Grant' in January 1988; this has provided a great boost to the research participants who are Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Lowry Piling, John Barnett & Assoc. and Imperial College London. The DoE (N.I.) are also contributing to a site characterisation study with TCD.

The Site

Boreholes and piezocone tests have revealed a site stratigraphy comprising $\approx 2\text{m}$ of alluvial clayey sands and silts overlying $\approx 7\text{m}$ of soft, high plasticity, sensitive clay (referred to locally as 'sleech'); this clay is underlain by a medium dense sand layer. CPT q_c values in the upper alluvium are typically $\approx 1.5\text{MPa}$ while those in the sleech are in the range 150kPa to 250kPa and representative of a very soft to soft clay. The water table is 1m

below the ground surface.

Lateral Pile Tests

Two 350mm square instrumented precast concrete piles, designated *LI* and *ALI*, were driven, 2m apart, to the sand layer at 9.5m. Both piles had centrally placed inclinometer tubes, each of which housed a string of high resolution electrolevels for monitoring pile displacement profiles. They also contained strategically located pressure cells in addition to electrical and vibrating strain gauges on the piles' reinforcing bars.

The soil in front of each pile was removed to a depth of 0.85m to reduce the effect of the stiffer near surface material on the lateral pile response. An axial load of 460kN was then applied to pile *ALI* while leaving pile *LI* with no vertical load.

The 460kN, which was equivalent to the total weight of the loading frame and kentledge employed, induced a pile head settlement of 1.8mm and was maintained while subjecting both *ALI* and *LI* to a maximum lateral load of 60kN one day after applying the vertical load. The vertical load on *ALI* was subsequently reduced to 250kN and the piles were re-loaded on the following day to a maximum lateral load of 89kN at which point the lateral displacement at both pile heads was 45 mm; see Figure 1.

The mechanism used to load the head of pile *ALI* included rollers at the underside of the beam supporting the kentledge and a pin just above the pile collar. The system was designed to permit free rotation and lateral displacement at the pile head while

allowing the vertical load to be carried centrally on the pile. However, strain gauge measurements made above ground level indicated that friction had caused the application of a small (righting) moment to the pile head. It was fortunate that the instrumentation allowed this moment to be measured reliably, and allowed for when interpreting the test results.

One of the most interesting features observed was the ability of a vertical load, by transfer of positive skin friction, to lead to a stiffer response of the soil close to ground level. For example, the pile head movement of pile *LI* at a lateral load of 60kN was 24mm and that of pile *ALI*, even after correcting for the righting moment induced by the pile head mechanism, was only 8mm. Such a difference in movements could not be explained by natural variability of the soil.

Implications for the design of laterally loaded piles

While a more complete description and initial interpretation of these test results is provided in Lehane *et al.* (1999), the following findings have immediate implications for the design of laterally loaded piles:

(i) Lateral pile load tests are likely to indicate a lower lateral stiffness for the soil than would be developed under combined loading in service. However, as movements increase, the presence of a vertical load may contribute to a sudden collapse.

(ii) The response of a pile to lateral load is critically dependent on the

However, as movements increase, the presence of a vertical load may contribute to a sudden collapse.

(ii) The response of a pile to lateral load is critically dependent on the characteristics of the soil within the top five pile diameters below the ground surface. Improving the soil stiffness in this region could be considered as a cost-effective option at the design stage.

(iii) The assumption of zero or infinite tensile strength for concrete when estimating the flexural rigidity of a laterally loaded reinforced concrete pile can distort the interpretation of lateral pile load test results.

(iv) Side friction (particularly for square precast piles) plays an important role in controlling the response of piles at conventional working displacement levels.

References

Lehane B.M., Phillips D.P., Paul T.S. and Horkan E. (1999). Instrumented piles subjected to combined vertical and lateral loads. *Proc. 12th Eur. Conf. Soil Mech. & Geotech. Eng.*, Amsterdam, 2, 1145-1150.

3.0 Conleth O'Loughlin (PhD student at TCD)

Of particular interest in the field of geotechnical engineering is the long term settlement of soft soils such as peat. Current research at TCD has focused on the long term settlement predictions for peat both in the laboratory and in the field.

3.1 Geotechnical properties of Peat

Peat is generally regarded as one of the worst foundation materials. Peat is in many respects similar in nature to clay, in that certain correlations between material properties and behavioural parameters reflect that of clay. However, peat possesses certain geotechnical properties which are particular to organic soils. One of the most notable characteristic of peat is its ability to hold water. This unusually high water content implies high a voids ratio and high compressibility. The consolidation process is rather complex in peat as permeability decreases rapidly as stress increases. Primary consolidation tends to be short in peat; it is the so-called secondary phase of compression which is the dominant factor in observed settlements. This secondary settlement is often referred to as *creep settlement*, defined as change of volume at constant effective stress.

3.2 One-dimensional Compression Models

Terzaghi's one-dimensional theory of consolidation has proved reliable in estimating settlements in non-

viscous clays. This approach has limited use in predicting settlements in organic soils as many of the assumptions included in Terzaghi's theory are not valid for peat. In particular the assumption that settlements will cease when effective stresses become constant is not true for viscous soils. Additionally, the coefficient of permeability is assumed to be constant throughout the consolidation process, and strains are assumed to be small. Both of these latter assumptions are not valid in peat as permeability is observed to decrease rapidly as a function of voids ratio and observed strains in oedometer tests at vertical stresses of about 200kPa are commonly in excess of 90%.

Of the various constitutive one-dimensional compression models which have been presented in recent years, TCD have focused on the *abc* model proposed by Den Haan (1996).

The model has been dubbed the *abc* model as these are the three parameters which best describe the compressibility of the soil. Parameter *a* accounts for increases in direct compression due to an increase in effective stress; *b* describes creep straining due to changing effective stress, whilst *c* accounts for compression at constant effective stress.

Den Haan's approach assumes a linear relationship between *Natural Strain*, *Logarithm of Effective Stress* and *Logarithm of Creep Strain Rate*. Traditionally plots of linear or Cauchy strain (ϵ^C) against logarithm of stress are assumed to be linear in the virgin stress range.

However soft soils such as peat are better described by a linear relationship between logarithm of stress and *natural strain* (ϵ^H). Organic soils tend to stiffen more rapidly and cannot be linearized on $\epsilon^C - \log p$ plots. Figure 1 shows the consolidation curve for a fibrous peat on both $\epsilon^C - \log p$ and $\epsilon^H - \log p$ scales. It is evident that the use of natural strain is much more successful in linearizing $\epsilon - \log p$ data for soft soils.

Intrinsic time, is also introduced as a measure of the stress history of the soil, but more importantly it is linked to the reciprocal of creep strain rate by the creep constant *c*.

3.3 Application of the abc model

The *abc* model has been applied to a series of oedometer tests on samples of Sphagnum peat from Clara in Co. Offaly. This is a poorly humified peat with a Von Post Humification value of H_{2-3} , an average water content of approximately 1800%, specific gravity of 1.41 Mg/m³ and a Loss of Ignition (LOI) of 98 %. Attention has been given to this peat because of the TCD full scale field experiment currently underway at Clara. This (long term) experiment involves monitoring the settlement depth profile beneath a 25m² loaded area.

Figure 2 shows measured and predicted settlements for a typical oedometer test with a Load Increment Ratio (LIR) of 1. As can be seen from Figure 2 good agreement is obtained between

measured and predicted settlements. The time for primary consolidation (t_p) is typically short, with approximately 50% of the total settlement measured in 24 hours occurring during this period. During

primary consolidation, settlement is more difficult to predict due to the combination of both direct and creep strain rates. At larger values of time, creep strain rates dominate, and settlement is predicted to an acceptable accuracy for all load increments.

References

- Den Haan E.J (1992). The formulation of virgin compression of soils. *Géotechnique* 42, No. 3, 465-483.
- Den Haan E.J (1996). A compression model for non-brittle soft clays and peat. *Géotechnique* 46, No. 1, 1-16.

4.0 Pat Naughton (PhD student at UCD)

At present a new hollow cylinder apparatus (HCA) is being constructed at the Department of Civil Engineering, UCD. It is initially proposed to use this laboratory apparatus to conduct fundamental investigations into the constitutive response of sand sediments including the effects of the rotation of the principal stress directions and of the intermediate principal stress. This paper describes the instrumentation and data acquisition system (DAQ) that will be used with the apparatus.

The rotation of principal stress and the magnitude of the intermediate principal stress are of fundamental importance in soil mechanics. An example where gradual rotation of the principal stress occurs is embankment loading. As illustrated in Figure 1 the direction of the major principal stress σ_1 varies from element to element along the potential failure surface.

UCD HCA

In the UCD HCA, hollow cylindrical soil samples will be subjected to combined coaxial thrust - torsional loading and to independently controlled internal and external hydrostatic confining pressures. The resultant 3 dimensional deformational response will be measured by both external and internal (small strain) instrumentation.

The hollow cylindrical sample is of 71 mm inner diameter x 100 mm outer diameter x 200 mm high. The sample is subjected to three hydrostatic pressures using GDS

digital controllers. Two of these controllers are used to apply pressures to the inner and outer sample surfaces through flexible membranes, whilst the third controller will provide the sample backpressure. The three controllers communicate with the control program using GPIB under IEEE 488. The coaxial thrust - torsional loading system consists of a combined thrust - torque load cell and two zero backlash stepper motors with reduction gearboxes for applying the torsional and axial loads respectively. The stepper motors are directly linked to the control program.

Deformations are measured by both internal and external instrumentation. The internal instrument will measure small strains over the central gauge length of the sample. The axial deformation will be measured using two double axis electrolevels (Symes & Burland, 1984) and one single axis electrolevel (Burland & Symes, 1982). The circumferential rotation of the sample will be measured using the two double axis electrolevels mentioned above. The radial deformation of the sample will be measured using non-contact proximity transducers (Cole, 1978).

The external instrumentation readings will be used to control the test when strain value exceed predefined limits. Two LVDT devices will be used to measure axial deformation. An incremental rotator encoder will be used to measure circumferential rotation of the sample. The inner and outer radial deformation will be calculated from volume changes measured using the three GDS

controllers. The pressure and volume resolutions of the GDS digital controllers are 0.5 kPa and 1 mm³ respectively. The resolutions of the combined coaxial thrust - torque loading system are 0.001 kN and 0.001 Nm respectively. The resolutions of the internal and external instrumentation are 1 x 10⁻⁶ % strain and 1 x 10⁻⁴ % strain respectively.

All tests will be run under closed loop control. The control program will be run under LabVIEW and will be capable, initially, of carrying out PbR α and Pbq α stress path testing, K₀ consolidation and simple shear testing, where P is the confining pressure, R the stress ratio, q the deviator stress, b is a parameter relating the major and minor principal stresses to the intermediate principal stress and α the angle that σ_1 makes with the vertical. The sample stresses are illustrated in Figure 2.

References

- Burland J. B. & Symes M. (1982). A simple axial displacement gauge for use in the triaxial apparatus. Tech. Note. Geotechnique, 32, 62-65.
- Cole D. M. (1978). A technique for measuring radial deformation during repeated load triaxial testing. Canadian Geotech. J., 15, 426 - 429.
- Symes M. J. & Burland J. B. (1984). Determination of local displacements on soil samples. Geotech. Testing J., 7(2), 49 - 59.

Figure 1. Rotation of the major principal stress beneath an embankment.

Figure 2. Stress on a hollow cylindrical soil sample: A applied pressures and loads, B resultant sample stress and C principal stress showing rotation of major principal stress.

5.0 Edward Cosgrove (Ph.D. student, TCD)

The research is aimed at improving understanding of the behaviour of sand under cyclic loading and will assist the prediction of the ground settlement trough that occurs adjacent to the abutment of an integral bridge.

5.1 Integral bridges

An integral bridge is a continuous framed structure where the deck and supporting abutment and piers are integrated. Consequently, no joints or bearings are present in the main structure. Daily and seasonal temperature variations cause the abutment to be cycled into the backfill. Lateral earth pressures increase and a settlement trough forms which is spanned by a run-on slab (Fig. 2). The length of this run-on slab is the major uncertainty associated with integral bridge design and is the main focus of this research.

The volumetric strain induced in the backfill due to cyclic loading depends primarily on:

- Stress and strain levels in the backfill.
- Density of the backfill.
- Number of load-unload cycles

A range of imposed cyclic shear strains due to typical daily and seasonal temperature variations of an integral bridge (100m deck, 6m abutments) is given in Table 1. Typical at rest stress levels in the backfill at various depths may be estimated using conventional methods. The dilative response of

the backfill, whether positive or negative, depends predominantly on its placement density. However, as unloading/re-loading takes place, the number and amplitude of loading cycles have an increasing influence on the volumetric behaviour of the soil.

5.2 Laboratory tests

(i) Static triaxial tests

Initially, examination of the stiffness characteristics of sand under static loading was performed by conducting a parametric study of a database of small strain stiffness measurements made in triaxial tests on sand and gravels. This study is reported fully in Lehane and Cosgrove (2000) and a typical example of a prediction of footing settlement made using the expression developed is shown on Fig. 1

(ii) Cyclic triaxial tests

To examine the behaviour of sand experiencing cyclic loading, a series of drained cyclic triaxial tests were carried out at the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology by the author over a six month period ending in March 99. These tests were performed under cyclic axial strain controlled conditions at appropriate stress and strain levels and densities. A typical stress-strain hysteresis loop is shown in Fig. 3 and the induced volumetric strain versus the number of loading cycles is shown in Fig. 4. It is evident from Fig. 3 that each cycle includes a compression and extension phase, corresponding to active and passive pressures in the backfill. The deviator stress increases with the number of cycles,

as the sand densifies. This increase in density is illustrated in terms of volumetric strain in Fig. 4. After 20 cycles more than 50% of the total volumetric strain has taken place.

(iii) Laboratory scale model

A large scale laboratory model is presently under construction to examine the shear and volumetric strains induced in the backfill of an integral bridge (Fig. 5). A video extensometer camera will be used to measure the shear and volumetric distortions during each cycle of loading, for a range of stress and strain levels, for both loose and dense fills.

5.3 Cyclic soil model

A cyclic soil model is currently being developed to capture the pertinent cyclic soil properties observed in the triaxial tests and the scale model tests. This model will incorporate a modified hyperbolic cyclic stress-strain relationship together with an appropriate stress-dilatancy formulation. A series of analyses for various integral bridge geometries will be carried out to predict the increase in lateral earth pressure due to cyclic loading and the size and extent of the settlement trough formed.

References

- Lehane B.M. and Cosgrove E. (2000). Applying triaxial compression data to settlement prediction of shallow foundations in cohesionless soil. Geotechnical Engineering, ICE, (in press)

$$E_{v'} = \frac{E_{v0}}{1 + \left(\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_{el}}{\epsilon_r - \epsilon_{el}} \right)^n}$$

Eqn. 1

where $E_{v0} = A_E F(e) \left(\frac{\sigma_{v'}}{p_{atm}} \right)^{0.5}$

Settlement of footing (0.5x2.0m) on Toyoura Sand

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Strain Amplitude		
Approximate max. shear strains and displacements due to temperature variations (100m deck, 6m abutment)		
	disp.	γ
Daily (serviceability)	+/-6mm	0.2%
Daily (serviceability)	+/-12mm	0.4%
Annual (ultimate)	+/-30mm	1%
1:120 years (extreme)	+/-60mm	2%

Table 1

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

6.0 Myles Lawler (PhD student, TCD).

This summary draws attention to the the high shaft friction and low end bearing capacities measured in two instrumented continuous flight auger (CFA) test piles installed in Dublin boulder clay. Measured friction was greater than applied in standard practice while base resistance was significantly less than assumed in practice.

6.1 Field and laboratory work

Two CFA piles were instrumented and tested; a 450mm diameter, 12.3 m length pile and a 600mm diameter, 11 m length pile. Two vibrating wire gauges were attached, diametrically opposite, at each of the seven monitoring levels. In addition, thermocouples were attached to the reinforcement cage of the 450 mm pile.

A 1 m long section of 450 mm diameter pile was formed using the concrete from the 450 mm, test pile. The section was formed and tested in compression in the laboratory so that the output from the strain meters could be related to the load in the piles. The results were compared with sub-surface output from gauges placed in the test piles at the same depth and a composite calibration curve formed, as seen in Figure 1.

6.2 Instrumented pile tests

Pile caps were formed to distribute the applied load. The load was applied, in a maintained load test, by jacking off a

reaction frame connected to anchor piles. Strain measurements and temperature readings, in the case of the 450mm diameter pile, were taken during the pile curing process, prior to and during the load test. Applied load versus displacement curves are given in figures 2.

6.3 Pile test analysis

Shaft friction

How do the shaft friction profiles, shown in figures 3 and 4, occur? This was the main question arising from the investigations. The low magnitude of shear stress mobilisation near the pile head can be readily explained as being due to ground disturbance and low overburden stress.

Arching may cause a decrease in stresses in the soil near the pile base and a corresponding increase in stresses some distance away. This may explain the bias towards greater shaft friction at the centre of the 600 mm but not the 450 mm pile. However, a finite element analysis using a hyperbolic constitutive model (Duncan and Chang, 1970) and including a dilatancy rule indicated no evidence of this effect (see figure 5).

Initial shaft friction profiles derived from strain profiles developed before loading and corrected for the difference in the relative thermal expansions of the reinforcement and gauge steel indicated the development of significant, initial load transfer caused by concrete curing, as shown in figure 6. Figure 7 gives a comparison of initial and mobilised shaft friction for the 450 mm pile. The stress reversal

required from large, negative shaft friction did not inhibit the mobilised shaft friction.

As the concrete is placed under pressure, shaft friction should benefit from the rough pile-soil surface caused. Unloading and reloading of the pile was found to cause a stiffer pile-soil interface and hence a better shaft friction response.

There are other possibilities, however, such as the presence of boulders along the interface and the development of lateral concrete pressures against the bore wall. A non-hydrostatic lateral pressure curve is of the same shape as the mobilised shaft friction curve in figure 3. Finally, heat of hydration may cause pore water to expand more than the soil and cause a reduction in effective stresses.

End bearing

The well-known limiting end bearing capacity of $9c_u$ is about twice that mobilised in the pile test (see figure 8) for $c_u \approx 450$ kPa. Possible reasons include the curing of the concrete causing contraction of the pile upward relative to the bore, creating a gap. High shear stresses developed limited the amount of load reaching the base.

Arching may cause a distribution of stresses away from the base. Base disturbance and decompression at the base of the pile is considered to be of minimal effect in very stiff soils with good construction practice.

Reference

Duncan and Chang, A.S.C.E., J.S.M.F.E.Div., vol 96, 1970, pg. 1629-1653

Figure 3 Selected average shear stresses developed for different applied head loads (450 mm pile)

Figure 4 As for fig. 3 (600 mm pile)

Figure 5 Direction of the total principal stresses in the soil around a loaded pile.

Figure 6 Initial load transfer (450 mm pile) taking zero reading at the point of maximum temperature (≈ 32 °C)

Figure 7 Comparison of initial and mobilised shaft friction shear stress (kNm^{-2})

Figure 8 End bearing of the 600 mm pile (0.4 m from the base)

7.0 Bryan McCabe (PhD student, TCD)

The objective of this research programme is to develop an improved understanding of the behaviour of pile groups in soft clay. Full-scale instrumented pile tests have been performed at a Department of Environment (U.K.) site at Kinnegar, near Belfast. The project is primarily funded by the I.C.E. Research and Development Enabling Fund. Other sponsors include Lowry Piling Ltd. (plc), John Barnett and Associates Ltd., (CSA Group) and Imperial College London.

7.1 Field Tests

Field tests were carried out on 250mm square precast concrete piles, embedded to 6m in a soft sensitive grey silty clay material, locally referred to as 'sleech'.

The test programme consisted of the following stages:

- (i) Pull-out tests to failure on a 5-pile group (average spacing to pile width ratio=2.7), in addition to a tension test on a single reference pile.
- (ii) A compression pile group test on a new group, similar to the tension group. The tension single pile was pulled out, cleaned and reinstalled elsewhere, before being loaded in compression.

Further tests being conducted (as part of related research) include one-way cyclic load tests on the groups/single piles previously tested under static conditions.

7.2 Pile Instrumentation

In addition to the standard load test measurements of pile head load and displacement, the piles were equipped with the following:

- Vibrating wire and electrical resistance strain gauges to allow the shear stress distribution in piles to be interpreted.
- Pressure cells to measure radial-total stress at the pile-soil interface, from installation to load testing. These were located in the centre pile and one edge pile of the compression group.

7.3 Experimental Findings

Some of the experimental findings to date are as follows:

(a) Radial stresses: pile installation and loading

When the edge piles were driven after the centre pile, there was no appreciable accumulation of locked up radial stresses. The radial stress decay with time for the group differed little from the pattern observed from the single pile (i.e. centre pile). Small increases in total radial stress arose during pile loading, in both centre and edge piles.

(b) Tension load tests

An average group displacement of 25mm was required to mobilise the group capacity of 310kN. The load was shared equally among the piles. However displacements varied somewhat due to tilting in the group. The reference tension pile

failed at 70kN and implied a group efficiency of 0.89 in tension, and a shear stress distribution varying from 8kPa at 2.0m to 16kPa at the pile base. A moderately stiffer response to the average group pile was observed. The centre pile in the group exhibited greatest stiffness (but only up to 75% of the ultimate load).

(c) Compression load test

At 317kN, the group capacity was about the same as that in tension but clearly lower than expected given that a 10-20% base capacity component. Recent single pile tests indicate that the relatively low capacity may well be because of local variations in the consistency of the sleech. Ageing of the sleech may also be a contributory factor given that the equalisation period allowed for the tension group piles was 13 months but only 4 months for compression group. The centre pile was less stiff, and assumed 28% less load than the average of the corner piles. The pile cap behaved in a rigid manner in this test and all pile head displacements were roughly equal throughout.

A compression test on a single pile gave a capacity of 56kN which was slightly lower than the group average and much lower than its tension equivalent. Large end area piezocone tests are being performed to investigate local variations in soil consistency between the two locations and the influence of the pile cap is being investigated using an ADINA FE model.

Load-Displacement curves for Tension Group and Single Pile Tests

Load-Displacement Curves for Compression Group and Single Pile Tests

8.0 Samir Hebib (PhD student, TCD)

This three year project is funded by the European union under the Brite Euram programme and is called *EuroSoilStab*. The primary aim is to develop an understanding of the behaviour of stabilised peat. Both the engineering properties of the peat (such as compressibility and shear strength) and the chemistry of the peat-binder reaction are under investigation. A large-scale laboratory test is being carried out and behaviour of stabilised peat modelled using Plaxis finite element model.

8.1 Laboratory investigation

The first stage of the project was to investigate the possibility of stabilising highly organic soils using binders commercially available such as cement, lime, pfa and blast furnace slag. Two sites were selected for this purpose: Raheenmore bog (RA) and Ballydermot bog (BA), both of which are located in the Irish midlands. The peats tested were highly organic (organic content > 90%) and very compressible. Eight mixtures were tested at a binder content of 150, 200 and 250 kg/m³. Stabilised peat specimens were mixed in the laboratory and tested for unconfined compression at 7, 28 and 90 days curing time. From the test results, a cement mixture was selected for use in the large-scale laboratory test and full range of laboratory testing was carried out.

Block samples (measuring 1x1x1m) for use in the large laboratory testing chamber were recovered from

Ballydermot bog. Samples were obtained using a steel box, having three faces with sharp edges, which was pushed into a vertical face. Samples were wrapped in polythene and put in wooden boxes tight enough to prevent samples from moving during transportation to the laboratory. Four blocks were recovered from a depth of 0.5-1.5m and four others from 1.5-2.5m.

An instrumented chamber of 2.3m high and 1.68m diameter was used. The chamber allows a large sample to be loaded axially by a means of airbags acting on the top of the chamber. Settlements, pore pressures, earth pressures and temperature were monitored during the test. The instrumentation used was selected to minimise interference with the peat. 12mm long miniature pore pressure gauges were used. Settlement plates were made at TCD and fabricated from of polycarbonate sheets. Circular magnets were attached to the plates. The location of settlement plates was determined using a Hall effect transducer with characteristics sensitive to the magnet attached to the plates. The sensor was lowered down into a 38mm collapsible hose.

A stabilised column of 600mm diameter, 1.5m high and a stabilised mass of 0.5m high were formed. The amount of binder used was 250kg/m³ for the stabilised column and 200kg/m³ for the stabilised mass. The stabilised peat was left to cure for 90 days before being loaded in two increments of 20kPa, bringing the final load to 40kPa. The stabilised mass is currently being unloaded and reloaded and will eventually be brought to failure. Finite element

predictions will be compared to observed behaviour to assess the ability of finite element models to predict the behaviour of stabilised peat. A back analysis using parameters derived from observed results will be carried out.

8.2 Results to date

Test results showed that high strength could be achieved when stabilising peat. Unconfined shear strengths higher than 250kPa were obtained when using cement or mixture of blast furnace slag and gypsum as binder. The strength achieved doubled between 28 and 90 days curing time. Laboratory tests showed a significant reduction in compressibility of the stabilised peat. Compressibility was found to reduce with curing time e.g. it halved in the period from 28 days o 90 days. One characteristic of stabilised peat is its very high yield stress, which is about 350kPa at 90 days. Creep behaviour was also investigated and was found to reduce with curing time. This raises the question of whether stabilised peat in the field should be loaded after 28 or 90 days curing time. Small strains stiffness of stabilised was found to be strongly non-linear and was dependent on both strain and stress level.

Schematic of calibration chamber and pressurisation system

9.0 David Gill (PhD student at TCD)

Research involved both theoretical and experimental investigations of displacement fields surrounding deep pile and penetrometer installation in clay. A brief outline of the research undertaken and some of the findings are presented.

9.1 Laboratory experiment

A model test was devised that allowed the soil deformation caused by the installation of a penetrometer to be visually observed and measured using a video-camera system. This was achieved using a transparent soil contained within a glass test chamber.

Transparent 'soil' is created from silica and a pore fluid with a matched refractive index. Transparency of the material is made possible by the size of the primary silica particles, which are smaller than the wavelength of light ($< 0.02 \mu\text{m}$) and do not cause it to scatter. The pore fluid used in this study was blended from crystal light liquid paraffin and mineral spirits to give a refractive index of 1.456 at 20°C . The silica-oil slurry was consolidated in the test chamber to form a stiff specimen (the maximum consolidation pressure applied was 225kPa). Oedometer, triaxial and shear box tests were performed on the transparent material and have shown it to possess geotechnical properties similar to soft clay.

During the consolidation phase a steel outer casing supports the glass test chamber, and this can be removed to allow a clear view the

specimen during penetrometer installation. The penetrometer consisted of a round steel bar (12.7 mm in diameter) cut to give a flat tip and was pushed into the centre of the chamber through a vertical guiding tube. The soil displacements were recorded using a video camera capable of tracking the movement of distinct markers placed with the transparent soil sample to a resolution of 0.01 mm. The system comprises a monochrome video camera connected to a PC-supported videoprocessor, which processes the digitised image in real time. A sequence of images showing the installation process recorded by the camera is shown in Fig. 1.

9.2 Theoretical analysis

The theoretical prediction of soil deformation caused by the installation of displacement piles and penetrometers deep into the ground has proved to be a difficult problem to solve due in main to the complex soil behaviour and boundary conditions involved.

This research builds on an approach called the Strain Path Method, which considers the penetration process to be analogous to a fluid flow problem. The method assumes the paths followed by soil elements around a penetrating pile are the same as the streamlines of an ideal inviscid fluid.

A modified approach has been taken here which uses a standard finite element fluid dynamics package to produce velocity fields around penetrometers of different geometry and SPM theory to calculate the

inferred strains and displacements. The effects of friction on the penetrometer boundary and soil shear strength have been introduced in a qualitative sense by specifying a relative velocity on the penetrometer boundary and applying a fluid viscosity, respectively. A parametric study of these two factors has produced a 'best-fit' solution to solution the experimental radial and vertical displacement results for a flat-tipped penetrometer (Fig. 2).

9.3 Some conclusions

Experimental observations of soil deformation around penetrometers showed a greater complexity of deformational behaviour than was previously indicated. The numerical approach achieved an improved prediction of the soil displacements, although predictions of the displacement paths followed by soil elements in the near field are only approximate, as illustrated on Fig. 3.

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Fig. 1. Camera images of penetrometer installation.

Fig. 2. Radial and vertical displacements $5R$ behind the tip of a flat-ended penetrometer for the 'best-fit' flow solution and experimental measurements.

Fig. 3. Experimental and predicted displacement paths for a flat-tipped penetrometer